

Leveraging Digital Subcarrier-based Optical Interfaces to Maximize Core Network Capacity

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Abstract—The rapid increase in channel spectral width is outpacing the available spectrum of deployed fibers, leading to accelerated capacity exhaustion in meshed core networks. This paper addresses this critical issue by proposing the use of advanced optical interfaces that enable the selective allocation of digital subcarriers (multi-carrier transceivers). By leveraging these interfaces, the spectral efficiency of core networks can be significantly enhanced, thereby ensuring more efficient utilization of the existing fiber infrastructure and extending the lifespan of current fiber deployments. Results comparing the utilization of multi-carrier transceivers versus traditional single-carrier transceivers show that the former can significantly increase usable network capacity without increasing transceiver count. This advantage is especially evident at higher symbol rates, where fewer channels per fiber result in faster spectrum exhaustion.

Index Terms—multi-carrier, coherent transceivers, optical communications, transport networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) is an advanced digital signal processing technique initially proposed for its benefits in propagation, particularly in long-haul transmission [1]. Instead of transmitting a single high-rate carrier, DSCM transmits multiple low-rate, digitally generated subcarriers. This approach offers several advantages, including increased robustness against chromatic dispersion [2] and nonlinear fiber effects [3]. Recently, DSCM has found a novel application in coherent pluggable transceivers supporting point-to-multipoint transmission, which allows simplifying and reducing the cost of aggregation networks featuring a hub-and-spoke traffic pattern [1], [4].

Optical transceiver manufacturers continue to look for ways to improve the capacity of their products. However, current and next-generation transceivers are nearing the Shannon limit and fundamentally offer higher capacity by increasing symbol rates. This allows to reduce capital and operational expenditures per transmitted Gb/s but does not translate into significant improvements of spectral efficiency (SE) [5], [6]. This trend of expanding channel bandwidth has triggered interest in augmenting the usable spectrum of optical fiber, via solutions such as SuperC-band, C+L-band, SuperC+L-band [7] and even using the S-band [8]. However, these solutions demand deploying a new line system. When considering existing systems, which usually feature the 4.8 THz C-band, it is clear that fewer channels will be available per fiber as

the channel symbol rate increases. Channel count reduction has a particularly detrimental impact (by increasing blocking probability) in meshed core networks, as shown in previous studies [5], [6].

The obvious solution to accommodate the reduced number of channels per fiber is to adopt spatial division multiplexing (e.g., multicore fibers, parallel fibers) or the abovementioned band division multiplexing (e.g., S-, E-band) solutions. However, except for parallel fibers in dark fiber-rich deployments, all these solutions are capital-intensive (e.g., rolling out new fibers) and/or rely on immature technology (e.g., new types of optical amplifiers). A short-term approach to enhance the spectral efficiency of deployed channels is to better adapt the transmitted signal bandwidth to the actual demand. However, the adaptability of existing coherent pluggable interfaces is limited, with multi-source agreements (MSAs) typically implementing only a few symbol rates [9]. Notably, the OpenXR Optics forum MSA [10] specifies a coherent pluggable based on DSCM, which can dynamically adjust the number of subcarriers in use. Although this feature was originally intended for point-to-multipoint communication [1], this work exploits the impact of using it to have a more granular adaptation of the optical signal bandwidth to the actual traffic requirements in core networks. Hence, we numerically compare the usable network capacity of a C-band system utilizing single- or multi-carrier (DSCM) coherent pluggable transceivers.

II. SIMULATION SETUP

We perform network simulations of a C-band system employing single-carrier (SC) or multi-carrier (MC) transceivers within the Spanish national backbone network, as defined by Telefónica in the scope of the IDEALIST project [11], and the 48-node Japanese national backbone network [12]. Two coherent pluggable transceiver types are considered, modeling two generations of these devices: (i) low rate and (ii) high rate. In the low-rate scenario, the single-carrier transceiver operates in three modes at 63 GBd and five modes at 126 GBd, as shown in Fig. 1(a). These values are derived from the OpenROADM MSA [9] for 200 Gb/s, 300 Gb/s, and 400 Gb/s formats (63 GBd), and scaled up to 126 GBd (800G transceivers), with the additional inclusion of 500 Gb/s and 700 Gb/s formats to allow fine-grained capacity increments of 100 Gb/s. In the high-rate scenario, the single-carrier

(a) Symb. Rate [GBd]	Bit Rate [Gb/s]	Req. OSNR [dB]	Req. SNR [dB]	(b)
63	200	16.0	9	Inputs: demand rate (R), source (S), destination (D), set of deployed lightpaths (L), transceiver operating modes (T), spectral occupation of network links (S_{occ}) Outputs: Updated L and S_{occ} 1. Perform grooming and exit if there is available capacity for R in one of the deployed lightpaths between S and D . Continue otherwise 2. Calculate the shortest path between S and D 3. Check for available frequency slots in S_{occ} and calculate their required GSNR 4. Get the operating mode from T that minimizes the number of 25-GHz slots to transport R (multiple interfaces may be used). Exit if T is empty 4.1. if multiple combinations occupy the same number of slots, select the one with fewer interfaces 4.2. if multiple combinations still exist, select the one with the highest capacity 4.3. if multiple combinations still exist, select the one with the lowest GSNR margin 5. if the GSNR margin of the selected signal is positive, select the slots with the lowest positive margin and update S_{occ} , create a new lightpath in L and exit . If not, eliminate the operating mode from T and go to step 4
	300	21.0	14	
	400	24.0	17	
126	400	19.0	9	
	500	21.5	11.5	
	600	24.0	14	
	700	25.5	15.5	
252	800	27.0	17	
	800	22.0	9	
	1000	24.5	11.5	
	1200	27.0	14	
	1400	28.5	15.5	
	1600	30.0	17	

Fig. 1. (a) Single-carrier transceiver characteristics. (b) RSA algorithm description.

Fig. 2. (a) Maximum spectral efficiency and (b) channel capacity versus reach on a point-to-point transmission with 80-km spans.

transceiver operates in five modes at 126 GBd and another five modes at 252 GBd.

Despite the abovementioned potential performance advantages of DSCM, we adopt a conservative approach where the multi-carrier transceiver has 32 equal subcarriers (i.e., with the same symbol rate and modulation format) and its SNR requirements match those of the single-carrier transceiver at the highest symbol rate. This approach guarantees that any observed capacity gains are not attributed to using better coherent pluggable transceiver specifications. The bit rate (Bitrate^{MC}) and required OSNR (OSNR_{req}^{MC}) are calculated based on the number of subcarriers used (N_S):

$$\text{OSNR}_{req}^{MC} = \text{OSNR}_{req,max} + 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{N_S}{32} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Bitrate}^{MC} = \text{Bitrate}_{max} * \frac{N_S}{32}, \quad (2)$$

where $\text{OSNR}_{req,max}$ and Bitrate_{max} are the required OSNR and the bitrate of the MC transceiver with all 32 subcarriers, respectively. These values are equal to the highest symbol rate SC transceiver, i.e. 126 GBd in the low-rate and 252 GBd in the high-rate scenario.

We assume transmission in ITU-T G.652D optical fibers characterized by a dispersion parameter of 16.7 ps/nm/km @

1550 nm and a dispersion slope of 0.058 ps/nm²/km. Additionally, the frequency-dependent loss and nonlinear coefficient of this fiber type are the same as in [13]. The power transfer caused by the stimulated Raman scattering (SRS) is taken into account assuming the Raman gain profile of [13]. The C band provides 6 THz of available bandwidth and the amplifier noise figure is equal to 5 dB.

We calculate the GSNR of each transmitted channel as:

$$\text{GSNR}_i = \frac{P_i}{P_i^{ASE} + P_i^{NLI}}, \quad (3)$$

where P_i is the power of channel i and P_i^{ASE} and P_i^{NLI} are the power of the Gaussian noise corresponding to the ASE and the nonlinear interference at channel i , respectively. The amount of ASE noise added by the amplifiers on channel i depends on the amplifier's gain (G) and noise figure (NF) and is given by:

$$P_i^{ASE} = h \cdot G(f_i) \cdot B_{ref} \cdot f_i \cdot NF(f_i), \quad (4)$$

where h is the Planck's constant, B_{ref} is the reference bandwidth (in this work, we consider the reference bandwidth of 0.1 nm.) and f_i is the channel's centre frequency. The NLI power is estimated using the GGN model, resorting to the implementation available in GNPY that numerically solves

Fig. 3. Average blocking probability for different total loads for the (a) Spanish and (b) Japanese networks.

Fig. 4. Average number of interfaces for different total loads for the (a) Spanish and (b) Japanese networks.

the GGN integrals using the composite trapezoidal rule. The power evolution of each channel along the fiber considers the SRS effect by numerically solving the SRS ordinary differential equation system using the solver available in the GNPY library [14].

The amplifiers' operating points are optimized to maximize the average GSNR and minimize the GSNR ripple, following the methodology outlined in [13]. For traffic provisioning, a sequential Routing and Spectrum Assignment (RSA) policy is implemented (see Fig. 1(b)). Traffic demands are uniformly generated, with payloads ranging from 200 to 800 Gb/s (low-rate) and from 400 to 1600 Gb/s (high-rate) with 100G increments. Each demand is sequentially considered for routing over the shortest path, selecting the feasible modulation format and symbol rate/number of subcarriers that minimize the number of 25-GHz spectral slots required to carry the payload, provided there is no available capacity in already deployed channels. The algorithm selects those with the smallest positive residual margin from the available and optically feasible spectrum slots to preserve the best frequencies for the most demanding paths. The number of 25-GHz spectral slots occupied by a channel includes a guard band of 25-GHz to ensure negligible filtering penalties.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, we examine the theoretical advantages of employing multi-carrier transceivers in a point-to-point link with N_S

80-km spans. Figure 2(a) illustrates the maximum spectral efficiency of each transceiver type relative to the link length. The results show that across almost all reach ranges, there is a slight improvement in spectral efficiency with multi-carrier, which is exclusively due to the availability of a wider set of channel formats. The additional formats (possible by controlling the number of active subcarriers) can feature a more optimal match between capacity and channel spectral occupation. Further evidence that this is the sole reason for the differences observed is that a plot for maximum channel capacity versus link length yields the same values for both single- and multi-carrier transceivers (Figure 2(b)).

Secondly, we run the network-wide simulation over the two reference core network topologies for various offered traffic load values, assuming that single-carrier or multi-carrier coherent pluggable transceivers are deployed. Figures 3(a) and (b) plot the evolution of blocking probability versus network load for both transceiver types and rate scenarios, considering the Spanish and Japanese core networks, respectively. The most relevant observation is that a lower blocking probability is obtained by using MC transceivers for the same offered traffic load. This trend holds for both networks and when considering low- and high-rate scenarios. Hence, it is clear that always adapting the optical signal (number of active subcarriers) and channel (spectral width) characteristics to the traffic requirements can augment the usable capacity of core

TABLE I
LOAD AT A BLOCKING PROBABILITY OF 1% AND CAPACITY GAIN BY USING A MULTI-CARRIER TRANSCIVER.

	Spanish Network				Japanese Network			
	Low Rate		High Rate		Low Rate		High Rate	
	SC	MC	SC	MC	SC	MC	SC	MC
Load @ BP=1% [Tb/s]	83	113	66	100	35	45	27	39
MC Gain [%]	36		52		29		44	

networks. Moreover, given the significant blocking reduction observed with MC transceivers, these results suggest that the cumulative effect of exploiting this feature for every provisioned channel in core networks is higher than what the relatively modest spectral efficiency improvements observed in Fig. 1(b) would suggest. Figures 4(a) and (b) plot the evolution of the number of required interfaces (transceivers) versus network load for both transceiver types and rate scenarios. The number of required transceivers for the same carried traffic load is very similar for SC and MC in both scenarios and networks, providing evidence that the blocking probability reduction observed with MC transceivers is attained without resorting to a significantly higher number of devices.

To gain further insight into the network capacity improvements, consider the results in Table I, which summarize the average offered traffic load that leads to a blocking probability of 1%. For both transceiver types, higher loads can be reached in the low-rate scenario with traffic flows limited to 800 Gb/s, which is expected since doubling the traffic flow size and transceiver baud rate leads to faster exhaustion of spectrum as a result of the smaller number of channels. More importantly, in both networks and for both rate scenarios, the utilization of multi-carrier transceivers always results in a significant increase in traffic load compared to single-carrier devices. The improvements range from 29 to 52% and provide evidence of the effectiveness of adapting the signal and channel properties to the exact traffic requirements to improve the utilization of spectrum resources in mesh core networks. Another relevant observation is that the gain from using multi-carrier transceivers is consistently larger in the high-rate scenario than in the low-rate one (e.g., 52% vs 36% in the Spanish network and 44% vs 29% in the Japanese network). This highlights that using multi-carrier transceivers, or more generically solutions to better match signal/channel properties and traffic payload, will become increasingly critical when deploying in mesh core networks the next generations of coherent transceivers, featuring even higher symbol rates.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study delved into the advantages of employing pluggable transceivers with selective activation/deactivation of sub-carriers to achieve finer-grained channel bandwidth adaptation in mesh core networks. The findings reveal that these transceivers substantially enhance usable network capacity without increasing the number of transceivers required. This benefit is particularly pronounced at higher symbol rates (252

GBd), where the reduced number of channels per fiber leads to faster spectrum exhaustion.

Moreover, the ability to dynamically adjust channel bandwidths offers a promising solution to optimize network performance and resource utilization. By leveraging selective activation/deactivation, network operators can achieve more efficient spectrum management, potentially reducing operational costs and improving service quality.

Future research will aim to evaluate the impact of spectrum fragmentation in dynamic scenarios, considering factors such as varying traffic patterns and network demands. This will provide further insight into the practical applications and limitations of pluggable transceivers in real-world settings, paving the way for more resilient and adaptable mesh core networks.

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